

The Impact Of Self-Constructs Of English Teachers On Classroom Performance And Developing Students' Interest: A Mixed Method Study Of Public And Private Intermediate Colleges Of Karachi, Sindh

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Abstract

Teachers are considered the most essential wheels in the vehicle of any education system. Among many factors, the self-esteem and self-identity of English teachers need to be addressed properly that effects on teacher's performance. The study aimed at to examine the impact of self-constructs of English teachers on classroom performances and developing students' interest at intermediate colleges in Karachi, Sindh. The study sample was consisted of 493 college teachers of both male and female, an adopted self-esteem inventory "SEI" by Rosen Shine and self-identity questionnaire "SIQ", used in this quantitative study research design. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) reveals significant differences between self-esteem levels with teachers' experiences and qualifications. Result revealed that self-esteem and self-identity significantly contribute to the teacher's performance, $R\text{-square}=.749$ (71.1%). Self-identity was found the best predictor $=.704$ (68.6%) while self-esteem weak predictor, $R=.424$ (39.5%) of English teachers' performance. Findings of study also suggest that male private college teachers' self-esteem is very low and working under inferiority complex. While public college male teachers are in severe depression and failed to understand their role and responsibilities. Female private college teachers have got good self-esteem level with optimist approach. While female public college teachers are living under depression and confusion. Moreover, male private colleges' teachers must improve their identity orientation skills and recognize their self-identity scale properly. Female private colleges' teachers have identified their strengths and weaknesses to show graceful personalities. While female public college teachers failed to recognize their personality traits positively.

Introduction

Teachers have played the most dominant and crucial role in the development of any education system. Teachers' contributions and commitments have played pivotal role in the developing of students' competences. They further help to unfolding students hidden creative capability to make them confident, and critical. They are also known as brain and heart of any learning process. Among many factors, self-esteem, self-identity, self-efficacy, and self-confidence of English teachers' needs to be addressed properly because they always effect on teacher's performance. Self-constructs have significantly impacted on personality development job satisfactions and classroom performance of teachers. The present study investigates the impact of self-esteem and self-identity on English teachers' performances and developing students' interest at intermediate colleges Karachi, Sindh. It further explored that how teachers' self-constructs should be improved to enhance their classroom performance and students' interest and at intermediate level.

Self-constructs are basically the collections of the thoughts, ideas, feelings, and perceptions about oneself (Herman, 1996). It is a belief that you have created about yourself and see yourself? Self-esteem is a person's self-worth, personality traits to stable and enduring effectively (Savin-Williams, & Demo, 1983). The self-esteem can create positive learning environment for both teachers and students to show their performance and adjust themselves in the learning process. Self-esteem also refers to individual's understanding of one's feelings and self-worth (Sharma & Agarwala, 2015). Self-confidence and self-respect hold the positive or negative views regarding one-self as an individual (Sedikidies, 2003). According to the (1960), Rosenberg (RSES), self-esteem is measuring scale which identify the teacher's different levels of self-esteem in the social sciences.

Coring believes that self-esteem is the feelings of worthiness in racial, ethnic, and social groups (Coring, 2002). Evidence proves that the peace of mind and life satisfaction of an individual is strongly predicted by collective well-being for self-esteem (Katz, Joiner, & Kwon, 2007). The self-possession and spiritual representations of the body are dispositions of self-evaluation (Demetriou, & Kazi, 2013). In recent research reveals that self-

esteem has linked with inferiority complex and other social and psychological issues that brings depressions and melancholy to once life (Conger, Robins & Widamam, 2014).

Self-identity basically is mixture of identities orientation such as personality traits, approaches, and abilities of a person. It is also known as permanent self-assessments of an identity orientations which provide a meaning and focus on one's attention and immediate features of the context (Oyserman, 2007, 2009). Much research has been conducted on one general common notion of self-identity which informs that it is an active process where teachers must understand their identity through external forces or people's perceptions regarding you and your life experiences about that peoples (Flores & Day, 2006) and personal experiences and knowledge or other factors that effects on teacher's personality traits or teacher's identity orientations (Rodgers & Scott, 2008). Teachers understands who am I? Self-identity of teachers' have got much importance in the personality development and academic performance. Teachers' personality must be acknowledged, and it play a significant role in in the development of students' interest, performance, and personal development (Stenberg, Karlsson, Pitkaniemi, & Maaranen, 2014). Sachs, believes that (2005), teachers' self-identity provides an ample framework and opportunities to build up their own ideas and thoughts about their identity and how a teacher must be? How teachers should act and understand their roles and responsibilities. What should be their place and importance in the society? Thus, teachers should develop their self-identity for good social interactions and understanding their own strengths and weakness of their personalities. Identity also involves the teachers' personal emotions, connections, knowledge, and experiences. The importance of relationships and understanding of teachers' emotions and institutional developmental aspects needs to be considered effectively (Hagenauer & Volet, 2014). Teachers' identity is known as continuous dialogue with students, parents and colleagues for the progress and understanding of the student and performance of the teachers. It helps the teachers to develop an interaction with personal experiences, institutional and environmental learning development of the students. It guides both teachers and students to construct good relationship between them for effective learning process (Hagenauer & Volet, 2014). Teachers' emotional and professional identities are essential components for teachers' self-identity. Teachers believed that professional development can be determined the different traits for teachers in terms of how they teach effectively in the classroom, how they interact with their students happily and what are their approaches towards educational changes and improvements (Yan et al., 2013). Professional development and emotions have been reported factors which measures the teachers' identities and classroom performance (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009; William, 2012 & Baruch, 2014).

Machargo (1991) Self-concept may be defined as a set of values. It further helps an individual to describe about every individual is well familiarize about himself or herself about values related life situations. It is a personality development that indicates how teachers fit in the same class. When a student consider himself as the best themselves into the world and how they perceive about life. Self-concept depends on student's own academic ability and levels of learning and holds a positive self-concept about himself/herself (Acosta, 2007). The academic self-concept is based on two levels that relates how well we do in school or we learn. The first level describes the general academic self-concept where one is an up to date in all subjects. The second level is based on mathematics, science, social studies, and English language. Manning (2006) Self-concept is a psychological development that depends on some frame of references. It is positively correlations between academic performance and achievements (Baumeister, Campbell, Krueger & Vohs, 2012). Suggests that self-concept can increased students' academic performance and developing their skills, attitude towards effective academic learning process.

Research objectives

The following Research objectives were formulated:

1. To understand the impact of self-esteem, self-identity, self-efficacy, and self-concept on teachers' classroom performance at intermediate level.
2. To explore the effects of self-construct on teachers' classroom performance during teaching English at public and private intermediate colleges.
3. To find out that at what extent differ the public and private teachers' self-constructs during teaching of English at intermediate colleges.

Research hypothesis

The study was based on following hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is significant difference between the self-esteem level of male and female teachers at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the types of colleges public and private in self-esteem levels at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the age group-1 (26-36) and age group- 2 (37-46) in self-esteem levels of English teachers at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

H₀4: There is no significant difference between the male and female teachers in self-identity scale at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

H₀5: There is no significant difference between types of colleges' boys and girls in self-identity scale at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

H₀6: There is no significant difference between age group- 1 (26-36) and age group- 2 (37-46) in self-identity scale of English teachers at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

H₀7: There is no significant difference between public and private colleges in the classroom performance of English at intermediate colleges.

H₀8: There is no significant difference between the age group-1 (26-36) and age group- 2 (37-46) in classroom performance of English teachers at intermediate colleges.

Method

Research Design

The study design is quantitative in nature i.e., descriptive, and inferential statistics to investigate the problem. Thus, study was employed an adopted tool "SEI" Self-esteem Inventory, by Rosen shine and "SIQ" Self-identity questionnaire as research instruments. In self-esteem inventory, the participants were given inventory to fill in the blank next to each item by choosing a number from the given levels (4=definitely yes or almost always, 3=probably yes or often, 2=probably not or seldom, 1=definitely not or almost never). Similarly, self-identity questionnaire was designed which consists of 35 items. The participants were given the blanks to be filled by choosing a number from scales (1=not important to my sense of who I am, 2=Slightly important to my sense of who I am, 3=Somewhat important to my sense of who I am, 4=Very important to my sense of who I am, 5=Extremely important to my sense of who I am I)

Participants

The present study based on (493) participants teachers, both male and female from public and private intermediate colleges Karachi. Teachers were further divided (n=274) of male teachers and (n=219) of female teachers. Total no of intermediate colleges was (93). Colleges were further divided into two groups or types, namely (n= 54) boys' intermediate colleges and (n= 39) girls' intermediate colleges. The study sample was derived through a stratified random sampling technique.

The present study analysis the inventories which was consists of (20 items) showing to measure self-esteem of English teachers in 10 different areas.eg to what extent teachers understand their moral values and responsibilities. Are they able to be developing their interest during teaching English? A self-identity questionnaire designed which consist of 35 items and to know the teachers' self-identity that how they recognize their self- identity? What extent they are self-reliant and self-satisfied during teaching English. The data was analysis through SPSS package 20 version. The data was collected from all respondents' male and female teachers statistically through using variance analysis of (ANOVA) and sample t-test.

Results and Discussion

Concerning the first research questionnaire, the multiple regression analysis revealed that self-esteem and self-identity make significant contribution, R-square=.749(71.1%) to the prediction of performance of teaching English. Self-identity was found best predictor=.704 (68.6%) while self-esteem weak predictor, R=.426 (39.5%) of the performance of teaching English. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed significant differences in self-esteem levels with experiences and qualification of male and female, public and private intermediate college teachers.

Findings of Self-esteem Inventory for Teachers (SEITIC)

This research instrument will help the researcher to get better idea of how teachers at intermediate college see themselves. The item analysis is given in detail as under:

Table 1 Self-esteem Inventory of male teachers which shows total score of respondents with range of self-esteem.

S. N	Total Score of Respondents	Range of Self-Esteem	No:of Respondents in given Range	Percentage (%)
01	70-80	Excellent Self-Esteem	27	9.8%
02	66- 75	Healthy View Problem with Self-Esteem	63	22.9%
03	56-65	Neither High nor Low	67	24.4%

		Need attention		
04	46-55	Growth in your Self-Esteem	83	30.2%
		Depressed		
05	0-45	Severe Depression Urgent need for improvement	34	12.4%
	Total	-----	274	100

Table 1 reveals that the total (274) with (55%) respondents were male teachers of both public & private colleges, they filled this inventory, and after completing this instrument they were divided into five categories according to their score and range of self-esteem are given. In the first category, and of that (27) male respondents with (9.8%) that their range of self-esteem is Excellent. The second category, and of that (63) male respondents with, (22.9%) that they have got Healthy views and problem with their self-esteem, they need to improve their self-esteem. The third category, and of that (67) male respondents with (24.4%) that their self-esteem is neither High nor low, they need proper attention to upgrade their self-esteem on specific area. While (83) male, respondents with (30.3%) that, they must grow in their self-esteem. That they are depressed, isolated, and lives under the umbrella of melancholy, they need to work properly to get their self-esteem anyhow? The last category reveals of that (34) male respondents with (12.2%) that they live severe depression, their condition is very worse, this led them towards destruction. They urgent need is that they should get self-esteem. The condition of this category is very critical and needs immediate attention

Therefore, it is crystal clear that most of the respondents from male private & colleges' respondents should grow their self-esteem; they need to get rid from depression and melancholy to bring themselves into mainstream of self-esteem. Another important category of respondents is in severe depression. This is negative sign. It is urgent need of the time to improve their self-esteem immediately.

Table 2 Self-esteem inventory of female teachers which shows the total score of respondents with range of self-esteem.

S. N	Total Score of Respondents	Range of Self-Esteem	No: of Respondents in given Range	Percentage (%)
01	70-80	Excellent Self-Esteem	26	11.8%
02	66- 75	Healthy View Problem with Self-Esteem	63	28.7%
03	56-65	Neither High nor Low Need attention	56	24.5%
04	46-55	Growth in your Self-Esteem Depressed	60	27.3%
05	0-45	Severe Depression Urgent need for improvement	14	6.3
	Total	-----	219	100

Table 2 reveals that total (219) respondents with (43.8 %) Female teachers of both public & private intermediate colleges, they filled this inventory, after completing this instrument they were divided into five categories according to their score and range of self-esteem are given. In the first category, and of that (26) female respondents with (11.8%) that their Range of self-esteem is Excellent. The second category, and of that (63) female respondents with, (28.5%) that they have got healthy views and have problem with self-esteem, that they need to enhance their self-esteem. The third category, and of that (56) female respondents with (25.5%) that their self-esteem is neither high nor low, they need proper attention to upgrade their self-esteem on specific area. The fourth category, and of that, (60) female, respondents with (27.3%) that, they must grow in their self-esteem. They are depressed, isolated, and lives under the umbrella of melancholy, they need to work properly to get their self-esteem anyhow? The last category, and of that (14) female respondents with (6.3%) that they live severe depression, their condition is very worse, this led them towards destruction. They urgent need is they should improve their self-esteem. The condition of this category is very critical and needs immediate attention. Therefore, it is crystal clear that most of the respondents from female private & colleges' respondents have healthy view related to life and world, they have got problem in their self-esteem. Another important category most respondents need to grow their self-esteem to bring them into mainstream of self-esteem.

Findings of self-identity questionnaire for Teachers (SIQTIC)

This research instrument SIQTIC will help the researcher to get better idea of how teachers at intermediate college identify themselves. The item analysis is given in detail as under

Table 3 Self-identity questionnaire of male Lecturers which shows total 3 Scale items to be used individually by respondents in Identity questionnaire.

S. N	Total Items	3-Scale score of Respondents	Items to be used Individually	No: of male Respondents	Percentage (%)
01	(10 th Items)	27	Personal Identity Orientation scale (PIOS)	103	37.5%
02	(7 th Items)	21	Social Identity Orientation Scale (SIOS)	82	29.9%
03	(8 th Items)	23	Collective Identity Orientation Scale (CIOS)	89	32.4%
Total			-----	274	100

Table 3 shows that total (274) respondents with (56.2 %) male teachers of both public & private intermediate colleges, they had filled this questionnaire, after completing this instrument they were divided into three scale score (3-SS) according to their score and item individuality are given as under: In the first scale and of that (103) male respondents with (37.5%) that they got personal identity orientation scale (PIOS). The second scale, and of that (82) male respondents with, (29.9%) that they have got social identity orientation, they very are sociable and loveable (SIOS). The third scale, the number ninety (89) male respondents with (32.4%) that have got collective Identity orientation, they also got multiple identity and easily adjust themselves in the different environment and different situation (CIOS).

Therefore, it is crystal clear that most of the respondents from male private colleges' respondents come under the personal identity orientation scale, they got graceful personality and easily made their ground among the heart and mind of students. Another majority of respondents come under the collective identity orientation scale. The respondents of this scale got multiple identity; they are very famous among the students.

Table 4 Self-identity questionnaire of female teachers which shows total 3-scale items to be used individually by respondents in identity questionnaire.

S.N	Total Items	3-Scale score of Respondents	Items to be used Individually	No:of Female Respondents	Percentage (%)
01	(10 th Items)	27	Personal Identity Orientation Scale (PIOS)	80	36.5%
02	(7 th Items)	21	Social Identity Orientation Scale (SIOS)	63	28.7%
03	(8 th Items)	23	Collective Identity Orientation Scale (CIOS)	76	34.7%
Total			-----	219	100

Table 4. shows that total (219) respondents with (43.8 %) female teachers of both public & private intermediate colleges, they had filled this questionnaire, after completing this instrument they were divided into three scale score (3-SS) according to their score and item individuality are as given under: In the first scale and of that (80) female respondents with (36.5%) that they got personal identity orientation (PIOS). The second scale, and of that (63) female respondents with, (28.7%) that they have got social Identity orientation, they very are sociable and loveable, (SIOS). The third scale, and of that (76) female respondents with (34.7%) that have got collective identity orientation, they also got multiple identity and easily adjust themselves in the different environment and in different situation (CIOS).

Therefore, it is crystal clear that most of the respondents from female public & private colleges' respondents they come under the personal identity orientation, they got graceful personality and easily made their ground among the heart and mind of students. Another majority of respondents come under the collective Identity orientation. The respondents of this scale got multiple identity; they are very famous among the students.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis of the study were tested through the demographic variables to show the association between independent samples t-tests and differences resulting. As four of the demographic variables of the study were

tested and found into two categories (Genders, Type of colleges, Age of teachers, teachers' performance), the means scores of tests were compared and reported into two groups. The results of demographic variables are given as under:

Gender differences in self-esteem levels

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the self-esteem level of male and female teachers at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Self-esteem Levels	Male	274	2.57	.54	.563	.589
	Female	219	2.66	.52	.561	.587

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between the self-esteem of male and female groups. There was no significant difference as $p > .05$, in the self-esteem levels of male ($M = 2.57$, $SD = .54$) and female ($M = 2.66$, $SD = .52$); $t(493) = .589$, $p = .563$. The results show that gender did not an effect on the self-esteem levels null hypothesis is accepted in this case.

Difference due to type of colleges (public/private) in self-esteem levels

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the types of colleges.

Table 06: Difference in type of colleges in self-esteem levels at intermediate colleges. $N = 165$

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Self-esteem levels	Public	100	2.39	.49	.693	-.43
	Private	65	2.85	.69	.693	-.43

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between the self-esteem of male and female groups. There was no significant difference as $p > .05$, in the self-esteem levels of male ($M = 2.57$, $SD = .54$) and female ($M = 2.66$, $SD = .52$); $t(493) = .589$, $p = .563$. The results show that gender did not an effect on the self-esteem levels null hypothesis is accepted in this case.

Differences due to age group of teachers in self-esteem levels

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the age group-1 (26-36) and age group- 2 (37-46) in self-esteem levels of English teachers at

Table 07: differences in self-esteem levels due to age groups $N = 493$

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Self-esteem levels	Between (26 to 36)	315	2.56	.58	.107	1.536
	Between (37 to 46)	178	2.49	.49	.107	1.536

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between the self-esteem at age groups-1 (26-36) and age group-2 (37-46). No significant difference as $p > .05$, in the levels of age group between (26-36) years ($M = 2.53$, $SD = .56$) and age group between (37-46) years ($M = 2.49$, $SD = .49$); $t(493) = 1.534$, $p = .1536$ were found. These results indicated that both age groups did not an effect on the self-esteem levels of the teachers. Results suggested that there was no effect of age group -1(26-36) and age group-2 (37-46) on the self-esteem levels of teachers at intermediate colleges. Therefore, null hypothesis accepted and finding supports the researcher.

Gender differences in self-identity scale of teachers

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between the male and female teachers in self-identity scale at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

Table 08: Gender differences in self-identity at intermediate colleges $N = 493$

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Self-identity	Male	274	2.63	.56	.593	.579
	Female	219	2.73	.54	.593	.579

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between the self-identity of male and female English teachers. There was no significant difference as $p > .05$, in the levels of male ($M = 2.63$, $SD = .56$) and female ($M = 2.73$, $SD = .54$); $t(493) = .579$, $p = .593$. Results suggested that there was no effect of gender on

the self-identity scale of English teachers at intermediate colleges. Therefore, the findings suggest that null hypothesis is accepted in this case.

Difference due to types of colleges (male/ female) in self-identity

H₀₅: There is no significant difference between types of colleges boys and girls in self-identity scale at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

Table 9: No of colleges (boys and girls) differences in self-identity at intermediate colleges N= 165

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Self-identity scale	Boy colleges	97	2.51	.50	.586	-.41
	Girl colleges	68	2.69	.68	.596	-.41

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between the self-identity of boy colleges and girl colleges. There was no significant difference as $p > .05$, in the levels of boy colleges ($M = 2.51$, $SD = .50$) and girl colleges ($M = 2.69$, $SD = .68$); $t(165) = -.41$, $p = .596$. Results indicated that no of colleges (boys and girls) did not influence the self-identity scale of teachers. Results suggested that there was no impact of no of colleges (male and female) on the self-identity scale of the teachers at intermediate colleges. Therefore, the findings supported the researcher to accept the null hypothesis.

Differences due to age group in self-identity scales

H₀₆: There is no significant difference between of age group- 1 (25-35) and age group- 2 (36-45) in self-identity scale of English teachers at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

Table 10: differences in self-identity due to age groups N=493

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Self-identity scale	Between Age group-1 (26 to 36)	315	2.53	.56	.107	1.537
	BetweenAge group-2 (37 to 46)	178	2.51	.51	.107	1.537

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between the self-identity of teachers at the age group-1 (26-36) and age group-2 (37-46 years). No significant difference as $p > .05$, in the levels of age group -1between (26-36) years ($M = 2.53$, $SD = .56$) and age group-2 between (36-46) years ($M = 2.51$, $SD = .51$); $t(474) = 1.537$, $p = .1537$ were found. Results indicated that there was no effect of age group-1 (26-36) and age group-2(37-46) on the self-identity scale of teachers at intermediate colleges.

Therefore, null hypothesis accepted and finding supports the researcher. Results indicated that there was no impact of age group -1(26-36) and age group-2 (37-46) on the self-identity scale on English teachers at intermediate colleges. Therefore, the findings supported the researcher to accept the null hypothesis.

Difference due type of colleges (Male/ Female) in classroom performance of English

H₀₇: There is no significant difference between public and private colleges in the classroom performance of English at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

Table 11: Type of colleges (public and private) differences in the classroom performance of English teachers at intermediate colleges. N= 165

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Classroom performance of English	Public	100	2.41	.51	.693	-.43
	Private	65	2.86	.71	.693	-.43

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between the public and private colleges on classroom performance of English teachers. There was no significant difference as $p > .05$, in the levels of public colleges ($M = 2.41$, $SD = .51$) and private sectors ($M = 2.86$, $SD = .71$); $t(165) = -.41$, $p = .693$. Results revealed that there was no effect of types of colleges on classroom performance of English teachers at intermediate colleges. Therefore, findings supported to the researcher that null hypothesis is accepted.

Differences due to age group in classroom performance of English teachers

H₀₈: There is no significant difference between the age group-1 (26-36) and age group- 2 (37-46) in classroom performance of English teachers at intermediate colleges in Karachi.

Table 12: differences in classroom performance of English teachers due to age group N=493

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	p-value	t-value
Classroom performance of English Teachers	Between Age group 1(26 to 36)	315	2.56	.59	.109	1.537
	Between Age group-2 (37 to 46)	178	2.51	.50	.109	1.537

An independent-samples t-test reveals the comparison the difference between classroom performance of English teachers at the age group-1 (26-36) and age group-2 (37-46 years). No significant difference as $p > .05$, in the age level between groups 26-36 years ($M = 2.56$, $SD = .59$) and age level between groups 37-46 years ($M = 2.51$, $SD = .50$); $t(493) = 1.109$, $p = .1537$ were found. Results indicated that there was no effect of age group-1(26-36) and age group-2(37-46) on classroom performance English teachers at intermediate colleges.

Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, and findings supported to the researcher. Results indicated that there was no impact of age group-1(26-36) and age group-2(37-46) on classroom performance English teachers at intermediate colleges.

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for self-esteem levels

H₀ 9: There is no significant difference between in the self-esteem levels of teachers with their teaching experiences.

Table 13 (a): differences high and low teaching experience with self-esteem levels

No.	Main Variable	Groups and Sub-groups	Sum of squares	Mean square	df	p-value	F-value	Result
14	Self-esteem levels	Teaching experience: < above than 5 yrs above than 8yrs Less than 8 yrs > above than 12yrs less than 12yrs > above than 15yrs Less than 15 yrs	b/w groups: 4-8 within groups: 10-15 total: 15 yrs	1.04 .28	5 491 493	.007	3.54	Sig

(ANOVA) test was conducted to compare the differences between English teachers teaching experiences on self-esteem levels. There was significant difference between teaching experience of teachers on self-esteem levels as $p < .05$ for the four levels [$F(4, 375) = 3.54$, $p = 0.007$]. Therefore, result indicated that thus null hypothesis rejected.

Table 13(b): Post hoc Comparisons of Levels of teaching experiences in self-esteem levels.

S. No.	Teaching Experiences of teachers	N	Mean	SD
1	5 & less	73	2.56	0.68
2	6 -10	271	2.47	0.47
3	Self-esteem levels 11-15	98	2.64	0.51
4	16-20	51	2.75	0.63
Total		493	2-64	0.59

Post hoc comparisons, using the Tukey HSD test, indicated that the mean score of the teaching experience of teachers above 16 years ($M = 2.75$, $SD = 0.63$) was significantly different than the teaching experience of 6 to 10 years ($M = 2.47$, $SD = 0.47$). However, the teaching experience of less than five years ($M = 2.56$, $SD = 0.68$) and 11 to 15 years ($M = 2.64$, $SD = 0.51$) did not significantly differ from the experience of 6 to 10 years and above 15 years' teaching experience of teachers at intermediate colleges. Results suggest that high experienced

teachers really do influence their self-esteem levels of the students. Findings of this study indicate that the teachers whose experience is sound enough can teach English effectively to their students in the classroom and in return their self-esteem levels will be improved. In short, this study reveals that teachers should possess high experience to increase their self-esteem level for better performance of their students.

Differences due to education of teachers with self-esteem levels

H₀11: There is significant difference between the teachers' self-esteem levels: (BSc, B.A / BS, M.A/M.Sc. MPhil, Diploma/ certificates,)

Table 14 (a): Difference in education of teachers to self-esteem levels

No.	Main Variable	Groups and Sub-groups	Sum of squares	Mean square	df	p-value	F-value	Result
14	Self-esteem levels	Teachers Qualifications: BSc/BS M.A/M.Sc. MPhil, Diploma/ certificate	b/w groups: 3.50 within groups: 112.33 total: 113.83	.88 .31	4	.025	2.96	Sig

(ANOVA) test was conducted to compare the effect of education on teachers' self-esteem levels. There was significant impact of teachers' qualification on self-esteem as $p < .05$ for the four levels [$F(4, 373) = 2.96, p = 0.025$]. Result indicates that thus the null hypothesis rejected.

Table 14(b): Post hoc comparisons of levels of education of teachers with self-esteem levels.

S. No.	Education level of parents	N	Mean	SD	Post hoc comparisons, using the Tukey HSD test, indicated that the mean score of teachers' qualifications in the category of above graduation level (M = 2.76, SD = 0.66) was significantly different than the category of certificate courses (M = 2.41, SD = 0.61).
1	B.Sc./BS	46	2.76	0.66	<p>However, the category of M.sc/ M.A. (M = 2.51, SD = 0.58), MPhil (M = 2.61, SD = 0.51) and Diploma (M = 2.71, SD = 0.58) did not significantly differ from the category of above graduation and Diploma/ certificate course level of teachers' qualification of the respondents at intermediate colleges. Results suggested that above graduation level of qualification of teachers really do influence the self-esteem levels of the teachers. The study Findings reveals that the teachers whose qualification level is above graduation they deliver better due to their self-esteem level towards their students in comparison with those teachers whose self-esteem levels is poor due to less qualification or experiences. In short, this study indicates that teachers who possess higher qualification at intermediate level, their self-esteem levels are better resultantly they performance well in the classroom learning that helps to improve students' performance.</p>
2	M.Sc./M. A	293	2.51	0.56	
3	MPhil/ equivalent	34	2.61	0.51	
4	Diploma	11	2.71	0.58	
5	Certificate courses	09	2.41	0.61	
Total		493	2.7	0.55	

However, the category of M.sc/ M.A. (M = 2.51, SD = 0.58), MPhil (M = 2.61, SD = 0.51) and Diploma (M = 2.71, SD = 0.58) did not significantly differ from the category of above graduation and Diploma/ certificate course level of teachers' qualification of the respondents at intermediate colleges. Results suggested that above graduation level of qualification of teachers really do influence the self-esteem levels of the teachers. The study Findings reveals that the teachers whose qualification level is above graduation they deliver better due to their self-esteem level towards their students in comparison with those teachers whose self-esteem levels is poor due to less qualification or experiences. In short, this study indicates that teachers who possess higher qualification at intermediate level, their self-esteem levels are better resultantly they performance well in the classroom learning that helps to improve students' performance.

Conclusion

The results of this study surprising and according to the expectations of the researcher. Male private college teachers' self-esteem is very low and working under inferiority complex which effects on their creative and

cognitive skills. While public college teachers are under severe depression and their self-esteem level is poorer and fail to understand their role and responsibilities effectively. Female private colleges' teachers have got good self-esteem level and are optimistic related to their work. While female public colleges' teachers' conditions are not satisfactory and live under depression and confusion.

Moreover, male private teachers have recognized their self-identity and personal identity orientation skills and got graceful personalities. While public colleges teachers are not capable to understand their roles responsibilities clearly and lives under the umbrella of collective identity orientation scale which help them to become famous among their friends and students too. Female private colleges' teachers are sound enough to recognize their personal identity scale to utilize their skills to get wonderful successes. They further promote their personal orientation scale to make themselves successful before their students and colleagues. While female public college teachers are poorest in this area. They are less confident not capable to understand their roles and responsibilities properly. They can utilize themselves by using collective identity orientation scale to do their work effectively but somehow, they failed to understand their students' needs and demands during English learning.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that certain effective strategies e.g., positive affirmations, praise and reward efforts and strengths-based activities should be set to eliminate negative labels of male private colleges' teachers. While public college teachers' conditions are quite worse, their pessimistic attitude, social anxiety levels should be seriously addressed to adopt certain effective strategies to overcome their flaws and polish their self-esteem levels.

2. Female private colleges' teachers should also use effective strategies e.g., be a good role model, positive affirmations, and strength-based activities to eliminate their complexities and recognize their strengths for better position. While female public college teachers' self-esteem levels should be strengthening and appreciate their working conditions to improve their self-worth. Proper strategies like, accept mistakes and accept rejection and recognize practice should be applied to save them from melancholy and inferiority complex.

3. Male private colleges' teachers should improve their identity orientation skills and must understand their roles and responsibilities, strengths, and weaknesses. They should be more committed and utilize their characteristics to enhance their identity orientation scale to get graceful personalities. While male public colleges' teachers should positively understand their strengths and accept challenges to recognize their self-identity. They should bring themselves under identity orientations scale to adopt goal-oriented strategies.

4. Female private colleges' teachers should fully utilize their personal identity orientation skills to get milestone success in their career. They should work hard to get collective orientation scale to update their identities. While female public colleges' teachers fall under the collective orientation scale and eliminate their difficulties to fully express their characteristics to bring them into collective identity orientation scale to understand their own strengths and weaknesses.

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